

Research

Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy, Innovative Behavior, Formal Credit Access: The Impact on Micro and Small Enterprises' Success

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Abstract: *The research aim is to analyze Entrepreneurial Self-efficacy, Innovative Behavior, Formal Credit Access, and its impact on Micro and Small Enterprises' (MSEs) success. Determining variables that support business success is important because MSEs are the backbones of a country's economic. The challenge for the government is that MSEs fail in the first three years. High Entrepreneurial Self-efficacy fosters an attitude to find opportunities, and able to withstand challenges. Innovative behavior leads MSEs to find, try, and implement new ideas. Capital needs can be met by having formal credit access. The survey was conducted on a sample determined through purposive sampling. Data processing uses multiple linear regression. The results showed that Entrepreneurial Self-efficacy, Innovative Behavior, and Formal Credit Access simultaneously have a positive impact on the MSEs' success. Entrepreneurial Self-efficacy and Formal Credit Access partially have an impact on the MSEs' success, while Innovative Behavior has no partial impact on the MSEs' success.*

Keywords: *Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy, Innovative Behavior, Formal Credit Access, Business Success.*

I. Introduction

Micro and Small Enterprises (MSEs) have a major role in reducing unemployment and having a positive impact on country's economic growth. Nationally, micro businesses absorb around 107.2 million workers (89.2%) and small businesses 5.7 million (4.74%), it means that MSEs absorbs a workforce of 94.9% in Indonesia (Ukmindonesia, 2018). Successful MSE can increase people's income and consumption that have an impact on increasing government

consumption, it will drive national economic growth. However, the failure of MSEs in the first three years is still relatively high. The failure of MSEs is caused by several factors including the lack of confidence of entrepreneur in their ability to run and manage a business, unable to face business competition, and have limited funds. Entrepreneurial self-efficacy is an important factor in every success in business. Having confidence and belief in the ability to manage and run a business, will foster an attitude entrepreneurial to look for opportunities, keep going ahead and be able to survive facing challenges in business. Innovative behavior leads entrepreneur to find, try and implement new ideas. Financing is important for companies because it helps in expanding operation, innovation, and investment. The capital needs of MSEs can be met by having formal credit access. Funding from formal institutions allow them to have the necessary funds that they need to develop their business. Previous studies, self-efficacy has a significant positive impact on business success or performance (Dessyana & Dwi Riyanti, 2017); (Ngek, 2015), innovative behavior has a significant positive impact on performance (Nasir et al., 2019); formal credit access has an impact on the financial performance of small businesses (Onyiego et al., 2017). Access to formal institutions have a significant impact on the success of small and medium-sized businesses (Riwayati, 2013), since there is a relationship between access to financial institutions and the growth of small businesses (Ibrahim Gumel, 2017).The objective of this study is to analyze entrepreneurial self-efficacy, innovative behavior, access formal credit and business success and the impact of these variables on business MSEs success.

II. Literature review

2.1 Entrepreneurial self-efficacy

Entrepreneurial self-efficacy refers to individual belief about their ability to find and take advantage of opportunities in the process of starting and developing a business (Klyver & Thornton, 2010). Entrepreneur's confidence in their ability to achieve business goal directly affects business performance (Baum & Locke, 2004). Individual who has a high level of self-efficacy, can do a good job and achieve a high level of performance. Conversely, someone who has low self-efficacy has an impact on unproductive actions that become obstacles to change towards improvement. Self-efficacy is needed in order to complete tasks aimed to the successful achievement, confidence in their ability to be able to complete the task, self-efficacy determines the effort to get through an uncertain and fully pressure situation (Bandura

et al., 1999). Generally, entrepreneurial self-efficacy refers to an entrepreneur self-confidence in their ability to manage and carry out tasks intended to entrepreneurship-oriented to the results. There are five dimensions to measure entrepreneurial self-efficacy; searching, planning, marshaling, implementing people and implementing financial, (Mcgee et al., 2009).

2.2 Innovative behavior

Innovative behavior is an overall action emergence of ideas, recognitions, and applications of something new and useful in every aspect of the organization (Kleysen & Street, 2001). Innovative behavior is several processes, in which individuals generate new ideas, promote and seek support for those ideas, and produce new things that may be useful for organizations or companies (Carmeli et al., 2006). Innovative behavior is the intentional behavior that includes exploring opportunities and new ideas, can also include the behavior of implementing new ideas and applying new knowledge to achieve increased personal or business performance (Jong & Hartog, 2008). Innovative behavior is all actions intended to produce, introduce and implement new things that can be useful to achieve organizational goals.

2.3 Formal credit access

Credit access is the availability of loan services from quality financial services at affordable costs (Claessens, 2006). Credit access is a condition in which an individual has the right, to seek and make decisions about the use of loans within a certain period and pay interest according to the time agreed upon by the borrower and lender (Akudugu, 2013). Finance is a major obstacle to corporate growth. Financing is important for companies because it helps in expanding operation, innovation, and investment. MSEs use various methods to access finance such as internal and external finance. Internal finance is related to the sources of funds through personal savings, and funds from friends or family. Inability of formal financial sector to meet credit demand leads SMEs dependence on informal and semi-formal financial units.

2.4 Business success

Business success is capital that has been fulfilled, productive distribution and achievement of organizational goals (Primiana, 2009). Business success is analyzed by knowing the performance of a company. Performance refers to achievement of the company in certain a period of time. In general, performance is a picture of the achievement of the implementation of an activity, program, policy in realizing the goals, objectives, mission, and vision of the

company. Business performance is the result or achievement that is influenced by the company's operational activities in using the resources. Performance of micro small businesses is a level achievement of MSEs within a certain period of time as a result of the utilization of owned resources which can be seen from the level of sales, profitability, return on capital, and the level of customer growth. Indicators to measure business performance are sales growth, customer growth, and profit growth (Rapih, 2015).

2.5 Research framework

Business success is the achievement of business goals. Entrepreneur must have high self-efficacy to achieve business goals. The higher entrepreneurial self-efficacy which is owned by entrepreneur is, the higher its impact on business development is. (Drnovšek et al., 2010). Entrepreneurs with high self-efficacy tend to perform higher. Companies which is led by entrepreneurs who have high self-efficacy are faster to grow and more profitable than companies which is led by entrepreneurs who have relatively lower self-efficacy (Hmieleski & Baron, 2008). To be successful entrepreneur, they must have innovative behavior, because innovation is a specific tool of entrepreneurship (Drucker, 1985). Innovation is the main force to win competition among competitors. Capital is a major factor that must be met in every business process. The fulfillment of capital needs encourages the achievement of business success. Access credit from formal financial institutions is important so that micro small businesses can increase their business capacity. There is a relationship between access to financial institutions and the growth of small businesses (Ibrahim Gumel, 2017)). From this explanation, the conceptual model of this study can be explained in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Research Model

2.6 Hypothesis

Based on the research concept model there are 4 hypotheses;

H1: Entrepreneurial self-efficacy, innovative behavior, and formal credit access have a simultaneous impact on MSEs success

H2: Entrepreneurial self-efficacy has a partial impact on MSEs success.

H3: Innovative behavior has a partial impact on MSEs success.

H4: Formal credit access has a partial impact on MSEs success.

III. Methodology

This research uses a quantitative approach. Data was collected from respondents using a structured questionnaire consisting of 45 questions. Sample of one hundred and four (104) entrepreneurs of MSEs chosen from Bandung, Indonesia by using purposive sample with this following sampling criteria: “MSEs business that have minimum age of 3 years which is taken in order to be able to compare sales growth, customers growth, and profits growth from previous years as an indicator of measuring business success. In order to calculate the magnitude of the impact of variables quantitatively, multiple linear regression is used with the following formula:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1.X_1 + \beta_2.X_2 + \beta_3.X_3 + e$$

Y: Business success,

X1: Entrepreneurial self-efficacy,

X2: Innovative behavior,

X3: Formal credit access,

α : Constants,

β : Variable regression coefficient

e: Error

IV. Data Analysis and Interpretations

4.1 Validity and Reliability Test Results

Validity Test is carried out on 30 respondents in each variable. There are 19 questions about entrepreneurial self-efficacy variable, 10 questions about Innovative Behavior variable, 10 questions about formal credit access variable, and 6 questions about business success variable. The validity test results obtained r value is greater than r table 0.296 ($\alpha = 0.05$) so that the statement is declared valid. The results of the reliability coefficient of entrepreneurial self-efficacy variable is 0.934, innovative behavioral variable is 0.880, formal credit access variable is 0.949 and business success variable is 0.893, so that all variables are declared reliable because their Cronbach's Alpha value are more than 0.6 (≥ 0.6).

4.2 Descriptive Analysis

In this study, the entrepreneurial self-efficacy variable includes five dimensions which are searching, planning, marshaling, implementing people, and implementing financial, and they are explored in 19 questions. Descriptive analysis results show that the percentage of entrepreneurial self-efficacy is at the low category which is equal to 30.8%, at the medium category which is equal to 69.2%, then at the high category which is equal to 69.2%. Based on the percentage, entrepreneurial self-efficacy of MSEs is at the high category. The innovative behavior variable includes four dimensions which are idea exploration, idea generation, idea championing, and idea implementation, and they are explored in 10 questions. The result shows that the percentage of innovative behavior is at the medium category 29.8%, and at the high category 70.2%. The formal credit variable access includes two dimensions which are frequency in accessing credit and amount of credits obtained, which are explored in 10 questions. The result shows that the percentage of formal credit access is at the low category 22.1%, at the medium category 43.3%, and at the high category 34.6%. Based on the percentage, formal credit access MSEs is at the medium category. The business success variable includes three dimensions which are sales growth, customers growth, and profits growth, and which are explored in 6 questions. The result shows that the percentage of the success MSEs is at the low category 2.9%, at the medium category 48.1%, and at the high category 49%. Based on the percentage of the success rate of MSEs, MSEs success has almost reached 50%, which is at the high category.

4.3 Regression Analysis

Before conducting a regression test, the assumption test is first performed to obtain normally distributed data requirements in the regression analysis. The result significance normality test value $0.200 \geq 0.05$ indicates that data have normal distribution, there is no symptoms of heteroscedasticity. With a tolerance of $VIF \leq 0.10$ or value ≥ 10 , multicollinearity did not occur so that the requirements and regression models are met. The calculated F value obtained from the regression results will be compared with the F table value, as well as comparing values with the significance level using $\alpha = 5\%$ (significant 5% or 0.05)

Table 1. Result of F test (ANOVA)

Model		<i>Sum of Squares</i>	df	<i>Mean Square</i>	F	Sig.
1	Regression	754.535	3	251.512	29.610	.000 ^b
	Residual	849.426	100	8.494		
	Total	1.603.962	103			

Source: Research Results (processed, 2020)

Based on calculation, ANOVA result explains the fit for the research. The ANOVA test shows the significance level = 0.000 ($p < 0.05$). This significance means that there is an impact of all dependent variables on the independent variable. Hypothesis one (H1) which is “entrepreneurial self-efficacy, innovative behavior and formal credit access have a simultaneously impact on MSEs success” is accepted.

Table 2. Determination Coefficient Test Results

Model	R	R²	Adjusted R²	<i>Std. Error of the Estimate</i>
1	.686	.047	.455	2,914

Source: Research Results (processed, 2020)

This result indicates that the adjusted R Square (R²) is equal to 0.455. It means that entrepreneurial self-efficacy, innovative behavior and formal credit access contribute 45.5% impact to the MSEs success, and 54.5% is impacted by the other possible variables.

Table 3. Results of Multiple Linear Regression Tests

Model	Variable	Unstandardized		Standardize	t	Sig.	Hypothesis
		Coefficients		d			
		B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	-.884	2,546		-.347	.729	
	ESE (X1)	.24	.043	.579	5.551	.000	H2 Accepted
	Innovative_Behavior (X2)	.47	.08	.063	.594	.554	H3 Rejected
	Credit_Access (X3)	.101	.031	.241	3.242	.002	H4 Accepted

Source: Research Results (processed, 2020)

Based on the result, we get the following model of multiple linear regression equation:

$$Y = - 0.884 + 0.240 X1 + 0.047 X2 + 0.101 X3 + e$$

From the equation above, it can be seen that there is an impact of entrepreneurial self-efficacy (X1), innovative behavior (X2), and formal credit access(X3) on business success (Y). The regression coefficient variable is positive indicating that if the value of the variables increases, then the value of business success will increase too; and if the value of the variables decreases, then the value of business success will decrease too. The t test is used in order to show how far is the impact of the independent variables on the variation of the dependent variable with a significant level use $\alpha = 5\%$. The table 3 shows the results of the t test where we can see that value of entrepreneurial self-efficacy is $0,000 < 0.05$, it means that there is a partial impact of the entrepreneurial self-efficacy on business MSEs success, so that hypothesis two (H2) is accepted; the value of innovative behavior variable is $0.554 > 0.05$, it means that there is no partial impact of innovative behavior on business MSEs success, so that hypothesis three (H3) is rejected; and the value of formal credit access variable is $0.002 < 0.05$, it means that there is a partial impact of formal credit access on business MSEs success, so that hypothesis four (H4) is accepted.

V. Discussion and Conclusion

5.1 Discussion

The finding shows there is a partial impact of entrepreneurial self-efficacy on business MSEs success. This result supports previous research where entrepreneurial self-efficacy has a

positive impact on business success (Dessyana & Dwi Riyanti, 2017), entrepreneurial self-efficacy has a positive relationship on business performance (Ngek, 2015). Higher individual's beliefs about the ability to run a business, will have a greater impact on business development. Entrepreneurs with high entrepreneurial self-efficacy will greatly impact business success (Drnovšek et al., 2010). There is no partial impact of innovative behavior on business MSEs success. This result does not support previous research where innovative behavior had a positive impact on performance (Nasir et al., 2019); (Berliana & Arsanti, 2018). There is a partial impact of formal credit access on business MSEs success. The impact of formal credit access variable on the business MSEs success is positive, which means that any increase in the level of formal credit access to MSEs will be followed by an increase in the MSE success rate. This result supports previous research which showed that there is a relationship between access to financial institutions and the growth of small businesses (Ibrahim Gumel, 2017)

5.2 Conclusion

Entrepreneurial self-efficacy, innovative behavior and the MSEs success in Bandung, Indonesia are at the high category, while formal credit access is at the medium category. Entrepreneurial self-efficacy, innovative behavior, and formal credit access have a simultaneous impact on business success of micro and small businesses. It means that if the value of all variables which are entrepreneurial self-efficacy, innovative behavior and access formal credit increase, the business success increases too. Entrepreneurial self-efficacy partially has a positive impact on the MSEs success. Higher level of entrepreneurial self-efficacy impacts the increasing on business success. Formal credit access also has a positive impact on MSEs success, since the greater the level of formal credit access is, the greater the business success increases. Innovative behavior has no partial impact on business success so that innovative behavior does not directly have an impact on MSEs success in Bandung, Indonesia.

5.3 Suggestion

Considering the results of this study, it is important to increase self-efficacy among MSEs to improve MSEs success. It is suggested that government create a guidance and motivation program for MSEs that aims to allowing the sharing experiences from successful MSEs to the developing MSEs because a way to improve self-efficacy is to share experiences and guidance

verbal persuasion (Bandura, 2001). Formal credit access has an important role also for the MSEs success so that the government should continuously socialize the micro and small businesses about the existence of formal, bank and non-bank financing institutions because even if some banks are not engaged in the MSE financing segment, they can collaborate with linkage financing models, channeling with other financial institutions. Future researchers on micro and small businesses can make a study which will focus more on separating internal and external variables, with a wider number of samples and population in order to obtain more objective and comprehensive information.

References

- Akudugu, M. (2013). The Determinants of Financial Inclusion in Western Africa: Insights from Ghana. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting* ISSN 2222-2847
- Badan Pusat Statistik. (2018). Potensi Peningkatan Kinerja Usaha Mikro Kecil Jawa Barat, *Analisis Hasil Sensus Ekonomi Lanjutan SE2016*, Katalog : 9102062.32, Badan Pusat Statistik Jawa Barat.
- Bandura, A., Freeman, W. H., & Lightsey, R. (1999). Self-Efficacy: The Exercise of Control. *Journal of Cognitive Psychotherapy*. <https://doi.org/10.1891/0889-8391.13.2.158>
- Bandura, A. (2001). Social Cognitive Theory: An Agentic Perspective. *Annual Review of Psychology*. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.psych.52.1.1>
- Baum, J. R., & Locke, E. A. (2004). The relationship of entrepreneurial traits, skill, and motivation to subsequent venture growth. *Journal of Applied Psychology*. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.89.4.587>
- Berliana, V., & Arsanti, T. A. (2018). Analisis Pengaruh Self-efficacy, Kapabilitas, dan Perilaku Kerja Inovatif terhadap Kinerja. *Jurnal Maksipreneur: Manajemen, Koperasi, Dan Entrepreneurship*. <https://doi.org/10.30588/jmp.v7i2.364>
- Carmeli, A., Meitar, R., & Weisberg, J. (2006). Self-leadership skills and innovative behavior at work. *International Journal of Manpower*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/01437720610652853>
- Claessens, S. (2006). Access to financial services: A review of the issues and public policy objectives. In *World Bank Research Observer*. <https://doi.org/10.1093/wbro/lk1004>
- Dessyana, A., & Dwi Riyanti, B. P. (2017). The Influence of Innovation and Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy to Digital Startup Success. *Internatinal Research Journal of Business Studies*. <https://doi.org/10.21632/irjbs.10.1.57-68>
- De Jong, J. P. J., & Den Hartog, D. N. (2007). How leaders influence employees' innovative behaviour. *European Journal of Innovation Management*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/14601060710720546>
- Drucker, P. (1985), *Innovation and Entrepreneurship Practice and Principles*, New York : Harper Business Book.

- Drnovšek, M., Wincent, J., & Cardon, M. S. (2010). Entrepreneurial self-efficacy and business start-up: Developing a multi-dimensional definition. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behaviour and Research*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/13552551011054516>
- Hmieleski, K. M., & Baron, R. A. (2008). When does entrepreneurial self-efficacy enhance versus reduce firm performance? *Strategic Entrepreneurship Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sej.42>
- Ibrahim Gumel, B. (2017). Access to Financial Institutions Financing as an Instrument of Growing Small Businesses in Nigeria: An Empirical Study. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*.7(10)
- Osano, H. M., & Languitane, H. (2015). Factors influencing access to finance by SMEs in Mozambique: case of SMEs in Maputo central business district. *Journal of Innovation and Entrepreneurship*. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13731-016-0041-0>
- Kleysen, R. F., & Street, C. T. (2001). Toward a multi-dimensional measure of individual innovative behavior. *Journal of Intellectual Capital*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EUM0000000005660>
- Klyver, K., & Thornton, P. H. (2010). The cultural embeddedness of entrepreneurial self-efficacy and intentions: A cross-national comparison. In *Academy of Management, Montreal, August*.
- Mcgee, J. E., Peterson, M., Mueller, S. L., & Sequeira, J. M. (2009). Entrepreneurial self-efficacy: Refining the measure. *Entrepreneurship: Theory and Practice*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-6520.2009.00304.x>
- McGee, J. E., & Peterson, M. (2019). The Long-Term Impact of Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy and Entrepreneurial Orientation on Venture Performance. *Journal of Small Business Management*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jsbm.12324>
- Miao, C., Coombs, J. E., Qian, S., & Sirmon, D. G. (2017). The mediating role of entrepreneurial orientation: A meta-analysis of resource orchestration and cultural contingencies. *Journal of Business Research*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2017.03.016>
- Nasir, N., Halimatussakdiah, H., Suryani, I., Zuhra, S. E., Armia, S., & Mahdani, M. (2019). How Intrinsic Motivation and Innovative Work Behavior Affect Job Performance. <https://doi.org/10.2991/agc-18.2019.91>
- Ngek, N. B. (2015). Entrepreneurial self-efficacy and small business performance: The mediating effect of entrepreneurial mindset and openness to experience. *Problems and Perspectives in Management*.13(4)
- Newman, A., Obschonka, M., Schwarz, S., Cohen, M., & Nielsen, I. (2019). Entrepreneurial self-efficacy: A systematic review of the literature on its theoretical foundations, measurement, antecedents, and outcomes, and an agenda for future research. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvb.2018.05.012>
- Oktavianti, V., & Hakim, M. S. (2017). Pengaruh Literasi Keuangan dan Persyaratan Kredit terhadap Akses Kredit Formal pada UMKM di Surabaya. *Jurnal Sains Dan Seni ITS*. <https://doi.org/10.12962/j23373520.v6i1>.
- Onyiego, G. O., Namusonge, P. G. S., & Waiganjo, E. (2017). The effect of access to finance on financial performance of SMEs in Mombasa county Kenya. *The Strategic Journal of Business and Change Management*, 4(3), 335–346. www.startegicjournals.com

- Oyeku, O. M., Oduyoye, O. O., Kabouh, M., Elemo, G. N., Karimu, F. A., & Akindoju, A. F. (2014). On entrepreneurial self efficacy and entrepreneurial success: A conceptual and theoretical framework. *European Journal of Business and Management Online*, 6(26)
- Primiana, I. (2009). Menggerakkan Sektor Riil UKM dan Industri. *Ekonomi Studi Pembangunan*.
- Rapih, S. (2015). Analisa Pengaruh Kompetensi Sumber Daya Manusia dan Modal Finansial terhadap Kinerja UMKM Bidang Garmen di Kabupaten Klaten. *Assets: Jurnal Akuntansi Dan Pendidikan*. <https://doi.org/10.25273/jap.v4i2.685>
- Riwayati, H. E. (2013). Financial Inclusion of Business Players in Mediating the Success of Small and Medium Enterprises in Indonesia. *International Journal of Economics and Financial Issues*.7 (4),623-627
- Sulistiyowati, E., & Lestari, N. S. (2016). Faktor-faktor Penentu Keberhasilan Usaha Kecil dan Menengah (UKM) di Kota Yogyakarta. *Jurnal Maksipreneur: Manajemen, Koperasi, Dan Entrepreneurship*. <https://doi.org/10.30588/jmp.v6i1.282>
- Sulistiowati, S. (2018). Peningkatan Perilaku Inovatif Perajin Tenun Melalui Perilaku Berbagi Pengetahuan dan Efikasi Diri. *Jurnal Ekonomi Bisnis Dan Kewirausahaan*. <https://doi.org/10.26418/jebik.v7i3.27236>
- Ukminonesia. (2018). Potret UMKM Indonesia Si Kecil yang Berperan Besar UKM Indonesia. *Ukminonesia.Id*.<https://www.ukminonesia.id/baca-artikel/62>

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